

A novel synthesis of Z-(9)-hexadecenal in improved yields, from aleuritic acid

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Z-(9)-Hexadecenal, an important pheromonal component, was synthesised from aleuritic acid, using novel procedure, resulting in improved yields. Microwave-assisted technique was also applied in the esterification of aleuritic acid, leading to shorter reaction times and 98% yield of methyl aleuritate.

Z-(9)-Hexadecenal (**6**), is the key component in the pheromonal bouquets of several agricultural, lepidopteran pests, including *Helicoverpa armigera*, *Manduca sexta* and *Heliothis subflexa*. As part of integrated pest management strategies involving pheromonal trapping, a number of syntheses for this compound and its derivatives, have been reported by different workers¹. However, yields are generally poor and the procedures are quite tedious. We report herein, a facile synthesis of Z-(9)-hexadecenal, in improved yields, using aleuritic acid (**1**), the principal acid component of lac resin, as starting material.

Results and discussion

(+)-*threo* Aleuritic acid (9,10,16-trihydroxy, hexadecanoic acid), isolated from shellac, was purified by recrystallising it from boiling water (m.p. 100–101°C). It was then esterified², using novel microwave procedure, in dry methanol, to yield methyl aleuritate (**2**). The ester was further oxidized³ with sodium periodate in acetonitrile to obtain methyl oxo-nonoate (**3**). Compound **3** was subject to Wittig reaction, using triphenyl phosphonium bromide, hexamethyl phosphoramidate and sodium amide, at –73°C, to obtain the ester, methyl Z-(9)-hexadecenoate (**4**). Reduction of the ester with LiAlH₄, in N₂ atmosphere, yielded the corresponding alcohol, Z-(9)-hexadecenol (**5**). Finally, oxidation⁴ of the alcohol, with pyridinium chlorochromate (PCC), yielded the title compound, Z-(9)-hexadecenal (**6**).

Experimental

Melting points were determined in open capillaries and are uncorrected. FT-IR spectra (KBr/neat) were obtained on an ABB Bomem FTLA 2000 instrument, using SpectraTech sampling accessories. ¹H NMR spectrum was recorded on a Varian EM-360 spectrometer (60 MHz, TMS) and the GC-MS data was obtained on a Thermo Finnigan

(Trace) GC-MS instrument. Purity of samples were routinely monitored by TLC, using silica gel, CHCl₃ and I₂ as adsorbent, eluent and visualizing agent respectively. Microwave irradiation was carried out in a domestic Kenstar OM 9918C microwave oven.

Methyl aleuritate (2) : Naturally occurring aleuritic acid (**1**), having *threo* configuration (m.p. 95–97°C), was purified by recrystallisation from boiling, distilled water, to obtain pure aleuritic acid (m.p. 100–101°C). This pure aleuritic acid (0.608 g, 2 mmol) was taken in a 100 ml Erlenmeyer flask, together with 25 ml dry methanol and one drop conc. H₂SO₄ (catalyst). This was subjected to microwave irradiation at 30% level (270 W). The time of irradiation was optimized to 6 min, 20 s. The content was allowed to attain room temperature, followed by addition of 10% NaHCO₃ solution (2 ml), with stirring. The solution was transferred to a 250 ml conical, stoppered flask, followed by addition of diethyl ether (50 ml) and 90 ml distilled water. The flask was kept overnight in a refrigerator, after which, the residue of methyl aleuritate was filtered, washed with distilled water and dried under vacuo to yield (**2**) (0.471 g, 74.05%). The filtrate was again treated with ether (60 ml); usual workup resulted in a second crop of (**2**) (0.152 g). Thus, a total yield of 97.95% of the title compound, methyl aleuritate (m.p. 70–75°C), was obtained by the novel procedure ν_{\max} 3348 (OH), 1741 cm⁻¹ (COOCH₃). The methyl aleuritate obtained by microwave procedure was also successfully compared with standard authentic sample, using *co*-FTIR and *co*-TLC. The novel procedure was adopted to prepare 8.80 g methyl aleuritate, from 8.75 g of pure aleuritic acid.

Methyl 9-oxo-nonoate (3) : To a cooled (0°C) and stirred solution of (**2**) (8 g, 25 mmol), dissolved in a mixture of CH₃CN-H₂O (6 : 4, 53 ml), was added NaIO₄ (5.78 g, 27 mmol) in portions. The mixture was stirred for 30 min at

5°C, in an ice bath, and then filtered to remove excess sodium periodate. The filtrate was extracted with CHCl_3 (3 × 50 ml) and extract was washed with water, brine and dried overnight under Na_2SO_4 (anhyd.). Distillation under vacuum (b.p. 110–120°C, 724 mm) yielded methyl-9-oxo nonoate as a clear liquid (2.85 g, 60.91%); ν_{max} 1737 (C=O), 2721 cm^{-1} (H-C=O). The other periodate oxidation product, 7-hydroxy heptanal, decomposed during vacuum distillation, and could not be recovered⁵.

Methyl Z-(9)-hexadecenoate (4): To a suspension of *n*-heptyl triphenyl phosphonium bromide (6.546 g, 12.6 mmol), in dry THF (30.1 ml) and hexamethyl phosphoramide (3 ml), was added sodium amide (0.494 g, 12.6 mmol) under N_2 atmosphere. The mixture was stirred at room temperature for 90 min. The dark orange ylide thus formed, was cooled to -73°C and the aldehyde ester (3) (2.35 g, 12.6 mmol), dissolved in dry THF (25 ml), cooled to -73°C, was slowly added to it. After completion of addition, the mixture was maintained at -73°C for further 15 min, after which, it was allowed to slowly attain room temperature. The solution was slowly quenched by addition of saturated ammonium chloride solution (50 ml). The organic layer was then extracted with ether (3 × 30 ml). The ether layer was washed with water, brine and dried overnight under Na_2SO_4 (anhyd.). Subsequently, the organic layer was concentrated under vacuo (b.p. 160°C at 10 mm) to afford the ester 4 (3.099 g, 91.52%), ν_{max} 1736 (COOCH₃), 721 cm^{-1} (C=C-H) (*cis*).

Z-(9)-Hexadecenol (5): To a suspension of cooled (-20°C) lithium aluminum hydride (0.437 g, 11.5 mmol) in dry THF (30 ml) was slowly added a cooled (-20°C) solution of ester (5) (3.099 g, 11.5 mmol) dissolved in dry THF (15 ml), with accompanied stirring. The mixture was stirred for 2 h at 0°C, followed by quenching slowly with saturated Na_2SO_4 solution (20 ml). The organic layer was then extracted with diethyl ether (3 × 30 ml), the ether extract washed with water, brine, and subsequently dried overnight under Na_2SO_4 (anhyd.). Concentration of the organic layer under reduced pressure (b.p. 130–137°C, 10 mm) yielded compound (5) as a light yellow liquid (2.556 g, 92%), ν_{max} 3399 (H-bonded OH), 1654 (C=C), 721 cm^{-1} (C=C-H) (*cis*).

Z-(9)-Hexadecenal (6): To a suspension of pyridinium

chlorochromate (PCC) (3.856 g, 17.9 mmol), in dry dichloromethane (DCM, 40 ml), was added a solution of alcohol (5) (2.556 g, 10.65 mmol) in dry DCM (20 ml) and stirred at room temperature for 3 h. Dry ether (60 ml) was added to the mixture and the solution was stirred for awhile. The solution was filtered through a pad of silica gel. This filtrate was concentrated on a water bath and then passed through a short column of activated florisil, using DCM as mobile phase. A thin pad of Na_2SO_4 was added to the top of the florisil layer. Removal of the DCM under vacuo afforded the title compound, Z-(9)-hexadecenal (6), (1.69 g, 66.64%), ν_{max} 2721 (CHO), 1727 (C=O), 1636 (C=C), 725 cm^{-1} (C=C-H) (*cis*); δ 0.8 (3H, t, CH_3), 1.3 (18H, br, $-(\text{CH}_2)_{11}-$), 1.8 (4H, m, $\text{CH}_2-\text{C}=\text{C}$), 5.3 (2H, m, $\text{HC}=\text{CH}$); m/z M^+ absent, 105 ($\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}$), 124 (C_{10}H_4), 147 ($\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{11}\text{O}$).

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